

A Study of Indium Alkoxides $\text{In}(\text{OR})_3$

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Manuscript received 29 April 1976; revised 21 June 1976; accepted 5 July 1976

Two alcoholates of indium trichloride $\text{InCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{EtOH}$ and $\text{InCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Pr}^i\text{OH}$, have been isolated. Indium tri-isopropoxide $\text{In}(\text{OPr}^i)_3$ has been prepared by the reaction of anhydrous indium trichloride with sodium isopropoxide from the medium of benzene and isopropanol. The insoluble methoxy and ethoxy derivatives precipitated out while these alcohols were respectively added to indium iso-propoxide dissolved in benzene. A series of other alkoxides $\text{In}(\text{OR})_3$, (where $\text{R} = \text{C}_2\text{H}_5^a$, C_4H_9^s and $\text{C}_5\text{H}_{11}^n$) have been synthesised by the alcoholysis of indium isopropoxide. The tert-butoxide could be isolated by the transesterification reaction.

ALTHOUGH a good deal of work has been carried out on alkoxides of various metals¹⁻³ including aluminium⁴⁻⁵ and gallium⁷⁻¹⁰ in group III, alkoxy derivatives of indium have not been isolated and studied so far. In view of this, a study of the preparation and properties of indium alkoxides has been undertaken.

Results and Discussion

In the attempt of drying tetrahydrated trichloride azeotropically by refluxing it with a mixture of dry benzene and ethanol, an adduct $\text{InCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{EtOH}$ was isolated. Another adduct $\text{InCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Pr}^i\text{OH}$ was isolated by refluxing anhydrous trichloride with dry isopropanol

The two alcoholates thus isolated are found to be crystalline white solids, soluble in benzene and parent alcohol.

The benzene soluble isopropoxide of indium could be isolated by treating anhydrous indium trichloride solution in isopropanol with sodium isopropoxide dissolved in a mixture of isopropanol and benzene :

Indium isopropoxide could be converted into the methoxide or ethoxide by treating it with the corresponding alcohol, mainly because these lower alkoxides are sparingly soluble in benzene and get precipitated from the reaction mixture :

(where $\text{R} = \text{Me}$ or Et).

Alcoholysis reaction¹⁻³ is now a well established technique for the synthesis of higher alkoxy derivatives of various elements e.g. $\text{Al}^{4,5}$, $\text{Ga}^{7,10}$. If the starting alkoxide is ethoxide or isopropoxide, the alcoholysis reaction is usually carried out in an inert organic solvent like benzene and the liberated alcohol is fractionated out azeotropically. The reaction mechanism may be presented, in general, as follows :

During the course of the present investigations, a series of other alkoxides of indium has been isolated starting from indium isopropoxide using similar procedure :

where $\text{R} = \text{C}_4\text{H}_9^a$, C_4H_9^s and $\text{C}_5\text{H}_{11}^n$.

The corresponding alcoholysis reaction with tertiary butanol was not successful in the isolation of tri-tertiary butoxide as the boiling point of isopropanol-benzene azeotrope (71.9°) is quite close to that of tertiary butanol-benzene azeotrope (73.9°). Similar to the tert-butoxide derivatives of aluminium⁴ and gallium¹⁰, indium tert-butoxide has been synthesised by the transesterification reaction¹⁻³ in the medium of cyclohexane, in view of the larger boiling point difference between tertiary butyl and isopropyl

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(2.425 g; 85.4% yield) were obtained by removing the excess of the solvent and were finally dried under reduced pressure. (Analysis: Found: In, 38.48, 39.25; $-\text{OPr}^i$ groups: 60.77, 59.63; Calc. for $\text{In}(\text{OPr}^i)_3$: In, 39.33, $-\text{OPr}^i$ group: 60.77%).

Molecular weight was determined in boiling isopropanol (15 ml) at different concentrations and was found to be 1162 at 0.4676, 1147 at 1.0026; average 1185; Calc. for $\text{In}(\text{POr}^i)_3$: 292. Average molecular complexity was, therefore, 4. Attempt to sublime the isopropoxide under reduced pressure was not successful.

Preparation of Methoxy and Ethoxy derivatives of Indium

Alcohol (methanol and ethanol) was added separately to a weighed amount of indium isopropoxide and the solution was refluxed for an hour when insoluble derivatives separated out. After the removal of the excess of alcohol, they were finally dried in vacuo. The results have been summarised along with alcoholysis reactions in Table 1.

Preparation of a series of Alkoxy derivatives by the Alcoholysis of Indium Isopropoxide

To a benzene solution of a weighed amount of isopropoxide, calculated amount (3 mole) of normal and secondary butanol and pentanol were added separately. The isopropanol liberated during the course of the reaction was removed azeotropically (b.p. benzene/isopropanol azeotrope 71.9°) and the excess of the solvent was removed by fractionation. The derivatives obtained were finally dried with the aid of a vacuum pump. The results are summarised in Table 1.

Preparation of Tert-butoxy derivative of Indium by the transesterification reaction

Tert-butyl acetate (20 g) was added to a cyclohexane solution of 1.5 g of $\text{In}(\text{OPr}^i)_3$ and the reaction mixture was refluxed properly for 1 hr. The isopropyl acetate formed during the reaction was removed azeotropically with cyclohexane (b.p. isopropyl acetate/cyclohexane azeotrope 78.9°). The derivative obtained (1.68 g) was finally dried with the aid of vacuum pump, and was analysed. (Found: In, 34.41, Calc. as $\text{In}(\text{OBu}^t)_3$: In, 34.64).

TABLE I—PREPARATION OF A SERIES OF INDIUM ALKOXIDES BY THE ALCOHOLYSIS OF INDIUM TRI-ISOPROPOXIDE

Wt. of $\text{In}(\text{OPr}^i)_3$ taken (g)	Wt. of alcohol added (g)	Compd. formed and yield obtd. (g.)	Physical characteristics	Analysis In(%)	
				Calcd.	Found
1.23	MeOH 10.0	$\text{In}(\text{OMe})_3$ 0.91	White powder (insoluble)	54.92	55.25
0.81	EtOH 10.0	$\text{In}(\text{OEt})_3$ 0.68	White powder (insoluble) (EtO-gp)	46.49 54.01	45.96 54.04
1.05	Bu^nOH 1.10	$\text{In}(\text{OBu}^n)_3$ 1.26	Light yellow coloured powder (soluble)	35.01	34.41
2.31	Bu^sOH 2.87	$\text{In}(\text{OBu}^s)_3$ 2.56	Light yellow coloured powder (soluble)	34.25	34.41
1.31	PentOH 1.18	$\text{In}(\text{OPent})_3$ 1.64	Yellow coloured powder (soluble)	30.23	30.55

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